

EXPOSURES TO NANOSCALE PARTICLES AND FIBERS DURING HANDLING, PROCESSING, AND MACHINING OF NANOCOMPOSITES AND NANO-ENGINEERED COMPOSITES REINFORCED WITH ALIGNED CARBON NANOTUBES

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SUMMARY

Concerns exist about possible exposures of researchers and laboratory personnel to CNTs, fibers (respirable and nanoscale) and nanoparticles during handling, synthesis, processing, post-processing, and machining of nanomaterials and composites containing CNTs. Prior exposure work is reviewed and new monitoring results focusing on abrasive drilling will be presented to balance prior work on cutting.

Keywords: exposure, fibers, carbon nanotube, CNT, nanoparticles, nanocomposites, polymer matrix composites, PMCs

ABSTRACT

Engineering of advanced hybrid composites wherein aligned carbon nanotubes (CNTs) are integrated into polymer matrices of existing fibrous materials is growing in research labs around the world. Real concerns exist about possible exposures of researchers and laboratory personnel to CNTs, fibers (respirable and nanoscale) and nanoparticles during handling of nanomaterials, as well as during synthesis, processing, post-processing, and machining of these composites. Exposures to nanoparticles, CNTs and fibers, may lead to adverse health effects, one major concern being cancer. This paper will bring to the attention of material scientists and engineers several potential exposure scenarios associated with handling, processing, or post-processing of advanced composites, health concerns around such exposures. New exposure monitoring results focusing on abrasive drilling will be presented to balance prior work on cutting. Exposure scenarios and their study is a critical step in establishing large-scale manufacturing processes.

INTRODUCTION

Exposures to raw (unpurified) long multiwalled CNTs were shown to cause asbestos-like pathogenicity in mice, such as inflammation and lesions when CNTs were introduced directly into their abdominal cavity (Poland et al. 2008), instilled into their lungs or inhaled (Shvedova et al. 2008; Shvedova et al. 2005). Asbestos exposure has been linked to scarring of the lung tissue (asbestosis) and development of mesothelioma, the cancer of the mesothelium or inner linings of the chest and abdominal cavities as well as the exterior linings of the organs they contain. Mesothelioma is a unique cancer associated with long fibers and is accompanied by a long latency period between exposures and cancer. The fibre length (particularly longer than 10 μ m), the aspect ratio (length/diameter ratio >3), enhanced biopersistence in the lung fluids, as well as presence of select transition metals and organics on their surfaces, have been recognized as key parameters in enhancing CNT fibrogenicity and carcinogenicity (Donaldson et al. 2006; Lam et al. 2006; Poland et al. 2008). Evidence continues to build on the argument that long, straight CNTs that resemble asbestos may behave like asbestos. Although attention has deservedly focused on the fibre-driven toxicity of CNTs, these materials, especially the as-produced (unpurified) types, can also induce significant toxicity to the lungs and other organs via particle-like effects. Exposure to nano-(<100nm) and fine (<1 μ m) particles, especially from air pollution studies and workplace exposures to combustion-derived particles, have been associated with respiratory, cardiovascular, and other systemic effects even at exposure levels of the order of tens of μ g/m³ and seems to be the case for raw CNTs (Li et al 2007). Skin exposure to nanomaterials (NMs), including CNTs, may also lead to possible adverse health effects such as irritation (Monteiro-Riviere et al 2005; Witzmann and Monteiro-Riviere 2006; Murray et al 2009) however, this exposure route has received much less attention and less is known about such exposures.

It should be remembered that the development of an adverse health effect is a complex function of exposure, inherent toxicity of the material (chemical), and individual genetic susceptibility and lifestyle factors. Exposure is undoubtedly one major factor in this relationship and the exposure route, its intensity, frequency and duration are important. For example, Fe is an essential metal for human health and oral supplements are oftentimes taken to provide the body with sufficient Fe. However, inhalation of Fe-containing airborne particles does contribute to lung toxicity. Similarly, inhalation of CNTs may lead to lung toxicity and possibly cancers, whereas direct injection of functionalized CNTs in the bloodstream is currently being explored for several biomedical applications, such as drug and gene delivery (Singh et al. 2006). The health risks can be substantially reduced or eliminated if exposures are properly controlled. Recognition of potential exposure sources to such nanoparticles, CNTs, and respirable fibers is of special importance as it will enable timely intervention to eliminating or reducing such exposures (Bergamaschi et al. 2006) and hence any associated health risks. The notable paucity of data on exposures to nanoscale particles and fibers associated with evolving CNT-based technologies for several years now add to the urgency of generating such exposure data.

OBJECTIVES AND APPROACH

This study had two major objectives: (i) To generate new exposure data for airborne particles during drilling of advanced composites containing CNTs; and (ii) alert material scientists and engineers about several potential exposure scenarios associated with handling, processing, or post-processing of advanced composites and health concerns of such exposures. For comparison purposes, drilling on base alumina composites (without CNTs) was also investigated.

Composites

The 'Fuzzy Fiber' reinforced plastic (FFRP) laminate, referred to here as CNT-alumina, is illustrated in Figure 1 (Garcia et al., 2008). The alumina-fiber composite without CNTs is referred to for simplicity as base alumina. Vertically-aligned CNTs (100-150 μm) were grown on a silicon wafer substrate coated with a $\text{Fe}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ catalyst layer by atmospheric pressure CVD in $\text{C}_2\text{H}_4/\text{H}_2$ at 750 $^\circ\text{C}$ (Yamamoto et al., 2009).

To fabricate the CNT-alumina composite, a woven Al_2O_3 fiber cloth was coated with Fe catalyst by dip-coating in a solution of $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ dissolved in 2-propanol. After catalyst coating, CNTs were grown ($\sim 50 \mu\text{m}$ length) on the fiber surfaces by catalytic thermal CVD. Epoxy was added to this CNT-grown cloth ply, and plies stacked and then cured to a laminate. Curing the epoxy was accomplished with heat ($\sim 50 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) and pressure ($\sim 200 \text{ kPa}$) to enhance epoxy flow through the CNTs and minimize voids. Thus, The CNTs in the CNT-alumina composites are distributed throughout the CNT-alumina hybrid composite laminate. The thickness of tested CNT-alumina composites varied from 1.7 (1 ply) to 2.8 mm (2 plies).

'CNT-alumina' hybrid composite

'CNT-carbon' hybrid composite

Figure 1. Illustration of the hybrid architectures used in this and prior work: (top) 'Fuzzy Fiber' Reinforced Plastic (FFRP) hybrid laminate with *in situ* grown aligned CNTs on the woven fiber surfaces (CNTs in blue and green); (bottom) 'nanostitched' composite with vertically aligned CNTs (VACNTs, in red) placed in between two plies of a laminated composite.

This pilot work investigated only the FFRP architecture in Figure 1, considering three major potential exposure determinants (factors): composite type; drill bit size; and drilling speed (Table 1). Due to the destructive nature of the tests, all available specimens (1-2 plies) were used. We did not attempt to control for the thickness of the specimen as this is expected to be less important during drilling than cutting. In a prior published study (Bello et al. 2009), exposures during dry abrasive cutting of two other types of composites (CNT-carbon and base carbon) were investigated. The synthesis of these composites is described in Bello et al. 2009. The CNT-alumina composite has $\sim 1 \times 10^{12}$ CNTs – cm^{-3} of composite.

Table 1. Summary of experimental conditions employed during drilling.

Composites	Base alumina				CNT-alumina				
	Ply#	Thickness [mm]	Volume fraction [wt%]		Ply #	Thickness [mm]	Volume fraction [wt%]		
			Al ₂ O ₃	epoxy			Al ₂ O ₃	epoxy	CNT
	2	2.3	67.5	32.5	1	1.7	61.8	36.0	2.2
	2	2.9	44.3	55.7	2	2.8	53.8	44.9	1.3
Diamond drill diameter	1/4'' and 3/8''								
Drill RPM	725 and 1,355								
Drilling	Dry and wet								

Exposure Monitoring

Airborne exposures to nanoscale particles and fibers were investigated during dry solid-core drilling of base- and CNT-alumina composites. Exposure data on drilling were generated during a single session and each test condition described in Table 1 was replicated five times. Several instruments were used for continuous, real-time monitoring of a broad range of particles sizes, number concentrations, and size distributions (>5.6nm-560nm; >0.5–20 μm), with additional post-sampling characterization of their morphology and size selective chemical analysis. Measurements of airborne particles (>5.6 nm – 1 μm ; 0.5 to 20 μm) were accomplished using a suite of instruments, including:

- A Fast Mobility Particle Sizer (FMPS Model 3091; TSI Inc., St. Paul, MN, USA), which measures the number concentration of aerosol particles in the range from 5.6 to 560 nm, for a total of 32 channels, with a response time of 1 sec.
- An Aerodynamic Particle Sizer (APS Model 3321; TSI Inc., St. Paul, MN, USA), which measures number concentration of particles in the range of 0.5 to 20 μm in 52 channels based on their aerodynamic diameter every sec.
- A condensation particle counter (TSI CPC 3007), which measures the total particle number concentration in the range of 10 nm to $\sim 1\mu\text{m}$ particles cm^{-3} , but *not* size distribution within this range.

- A thermophoretic precipitator (TP, Fraunhofer Institute of Toxicology, Germany) which uses thermal gradient to collect particles on a Cu TEM grid for electron microscopy characterization was positioned at the source.
- A WRASS (WRAS 005, Naneum Ltd., Canterbury, UK) was used to collect size-selective fractions of the aerosol over the whole inhalable range (<1 nm to 35 μm , aerodynamic diameter) in 12 stages.
- Sampling for respirable fibers (length >5 μm and aspect ratio >3) was conducted as per NIOSH Method 7400 with a commercially available asbestos sampling cassette (Millipore Inc., Bedford, MA; 25-mm, 0.45 μm pore size mixed-cellulose ester filter equipped with an electrically conductive 50-mm extension cowl and operated at 2 L min^{-1}). Samples were collected 10 cm from the source and in the breathing zone. Two filters were collected for each composite type in each location.

The laboratory layout is shown in Figure 2. Sampler arrangement for drilling (current work) and dry cutting (band saw, previous work) are presented in Figure 3.

Figure 2. Schematic of the laboratory depicting the relative locations of the drilling machine (current study), the band saw (dry cutting) and diamond saw (wet cutting) described in Bello et al. 2009.

Instrument inlets were positioned 10 cm from the potential emission sources (fixed distance and angle) or in the breathing zone of the operator. A wedge of each filter (from the cassette) was analyzed by SEM (JEOL JSM-7401F) after gold coating and by NIOSH Method 7400 (for respirable fibers) by phase contrast microscopy, whereas the TEM grids from TP and the WRASS sampler were analyzed by TEM (Philips EM 400T) for particle size and morphology. Elemental analysis for particles of interest was obtained with the integrated energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) detectors (EDAX) present on both instruments. Chemical analysis of each stage for Al and Fe (two major elements in the composites) was performed with inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) on an Agilent 7500cs ICP-MS system (Agilent Technologies, Yokogawa, Japan) based on the EPA 3051A method, which uses microwave-assisted acid digestion of samples. The ICP-MS analysis and quantitation of respirable fibers is still pending.

Figure 3. A and B. Schematics of sampler arrangement for the previously reported band saw cutting of the composites (Bello et al. 2009) and drilling. C. Schematic of the drill stage and sampler arrangement.

The suite of real-time monitoring instruments (FMPS, APS, TP) were positioned 10 cm from the drilling source at a 45° angle (horizontal and vertical). After five replicate tests, the inlets of instruments were switched to the breathing zone of the operator for personal exposure monitoring. A stationary integrated sampler (WRASS and the CPC 3007) was positioned to the right of the operator in the breathing zone area and symmetrical to the location of the real-time instruments.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Exposures to Nanomaterials During Fabrication and Dry Cutting of Composites

Exposures to airborne particulate matter generated during the CVD growth and handling of CNT nanoforests, as well as machining of two types of hybrid fabrication and the corresponding base composites without CNTs (the traditional types) have been reported previously (Bello et al. 2008; Bello et al. 2009). Several important findings of these studies study are summarized here:

- No significant exposures, especially in the nanoscale and fine (<1 μm) range were seen during growth and handling of CNT-grown CVD processes. No individual or bundles of CNTs were seen.
- Significant exposures to particles and fibers, especially in the nanoscale and fine (<1μm) range, were documented during dry abrasive cutting of all (base and CNT) composites, with maximum exposures resulting from thicker composites (examples in Figure 4).
- Respirable (length 5-20μm and aspect ratio >3) at a concentration of ~2-4 fibers cm⁻³ as well as true nanoscale fibers (with at least one dimension <100nm, often both dimensions being nano) were produced in all cases (base and CNT) of dry cutting.

In light of their composition, these particles and fibers are likely to be biopersistent and contaminated with redox-active transition metals such as Fe.

- No CNTs, either individual or bundles could be found in all these processes. It is likely such CNTs may be encapsulated inside the epoxy coating and register as particles larger than individual CNTs.
- Wet cutting almost always resulted in no exposures and seems to be an effective and advantageous processing method to dry, abrasive cutting.

Figure 4A. FMPS total number concentration (5.6-560 nm range) during dry cutting during of various composites. Legend: BZ-Breathing Zone; 1. Background; 2. Trimming edges of various composites; All others are for dry cutting of: 3. & 3'-base alumina, 4-ply; 4&4'-CNT-Alumina, 4-ply; 5-Base Carbon, 24-ply; 6-CNT-Carbon, 24 plies.

Figure 4B. Select TEM images of nanoscale fibers generated during dry cutting of composites in 4A.

Exposures During Drilling of Composites

Figures 5 and 6 illustrate the potential for significant exposure generated during dry drilling of composites. The graphs in Figures 5 and 6 present the total number concentration as measured by FMPS (5.6-560 nm), however, similar trends were seen for the APS. Some trends emerge from these data.

- Similar to cutting, drilling may generate substantial airborne exposures to nanoscale and submicron particles, as well as respirable particles as documented by FMPS and APS (data not shown).
- Higher exposures tend to be generated at higher speeds, with larger drills, and thicker composites. Similar observations were also observed for cutting.
- The CNT-alumina composite tends to generate less airborne particles than the base alumina composite of the same thickness, which is also consistent with prior observations during dry abrasive machining (cutting) of these composites and may be explained by the enhanced strength of the CNT-alumina composite due to the CNTs in the epoxy matrix.

Figure 5A. Drilling on base alumina at the source: Legend: 1 to 6, 2-ply: 1 & 2-low speed, 1/4"; 3-low speed, 3/8"; 4-low speed, 3/8"; 5-high speed, 1/4"; 6-high speed, 1/4"; 7 to 9, 2-ply: 7-high speed, 3/8"; 8-low speed, 1/4"; 9- low speed, 3/8".

- Based on the preliminary analysis of the filters and TEM grids, no CNTs-whether individual or in bundles, could be found in the air samples and the dust left behind by drilling (Figure 6). This observation is also consistent with findings of cutting of such composites. The CNTs apparently remain encapsulated inside the epoxy.
- Respirable fibers of similar morphology (long, thin, and with splints) were found in filters collected at the source and breathing zone for both base alumina and CNT-alumina composites. Preliminary data suggest that fibre concentrations will be much lower than those observed during the cutting of such composites. Initial EDAX analysis on the fibers did not find any Al or Si (markers for alumina fibers) or Fe (marker for CNTs) and the predominant elements were C and O. Chemical composition data suggest these fibers may originate from the fragmentation of the epoxy plastic component. Fragments of splintered alumina fibers were common in the dust sample (Figure 6, image E) but apparently very few of those became airborne. Select images of the fibers and EDAX are shown in Figure 6E, whereas select TEM images of particles collected on TEM grids are shown in images A-D. Chemical analysis of WRASS stages by ICP-MS may provide valuable information about the CNT contribution to airborne particles.

Figure 5B. Drilling on CNT-alumina at the source. Legend: 1 to 3, 1 ply: 1-low speed, 3/8"; 2-high speed, 3/8"; 3 to 6, 2-ply: 3-high speed, 3/8"; 4-high speed, 1/4"; 5-low speed, 1/4"; 6-low speed, 3/8".

- Breathing zone concentrations were generally lower than the source by one order of magnitude; however, potential for substantial exposures exists.
- Dry drilling of composites did generate visible smoke plume, especially for the thicker composites, suggesting potential exposures to organic thermal decomposition products of the epoxy components. The chemical composition of such exposures requires an independent investigation.
- Preliminary data suggest that wet drilling generates considerably less particulate exposures than dry drilling and seems to be a superior processing method and should be favoured over dry drilling.

Figure 6. A –D. Typical TEM images of particles collected on TEM grids at the source for base alumina and CNT-alumina composites. E, SEM image of the dust generated on the surface of the composite at the end of drilling showing fragmented fibers and epoxy fragments. F (scalebar 1 μm) represents the typical respirable fibre morphology seen under SEM and phase contrast microscopy on filters collected at the source and breathing zone. The EDAX image to the right of E and F suggest that such respirable fibers (image F) do not come from the fragmentation of the alumina fibers, but perhaps the epoxy composite itself. No clear evidence of CNTs (individual or in bundles) was seen in this preliminary analysis.

Other Exposure Scenarios: Recognition and Prevention

Few other studies have documented exposures to CNTs during mixing and blending of CNT-epoxy composites (Methner et al. 2007) and handling of unrefined CNTs (Maynard et al. 2004), raising again concerns about inhalation and skin exposures to such materials in

several settings. Anecdotal evidence suggests potentially substantial exposures to CNTs during blending of CNT raw material with polymers (to make polymer nanocomposites, PNCs) using commercial blenders and mixers. Processes that involve handling and mechanical agitation of powders, mixing powders, cutting, drilling, sanding, and similar processing of advanced composites may result in elevated exposures to the raw material (such as CNTs), as well as generation of exposures to fibers of different dimensions/morphologies and nanoparticles. Although factors that modify and/or determine exposure levels are poorly understood, it is believed that several processing parameters and other exposure conditions may play an important role. In particular, the morphology of the CNTs (powder, length, functionalization, forest, impurities and hydrocarbon by-products) and their method(s) of production must certainly be considered during exposure assessment. As an example from our prior work (Bello et al. 2008), no nanoparticles and/or CNTs emissions were observed during both production and post-production handling of long aligned CNTs grown into entangled forests (sometimes termed vertically-aligned nanotube arrays, VANTA). These initial findings are very specific to the CNT synthesis process and may not be generalized to all CNTs, and in fact may be specific to the synthesis process details (base growth of multi-walled CNTs, MWNTs, from a fixed Fe catalyst via batch CVD) used in that study. The preliminary data from cutting and drilling have identified several important exposure modifying factors, such as composite type and its thickness, the geometry and size of the cutting tool, and dry vs. wet processing. It is likely that much higher exposures may result during larger volume jobs and other combinations of above factors. It is therefore prudent to make serious efforts to control and eliminate such exposures through adequate engineering controls and the use of respirators, and engineers are encouraged to contact their environmental health and safety departments to discuss the need for monitoring and identify an adequate exposure control strategy. Additionally, materials scientists and engineers involved with such processes are encouraged to familiarize themselves with best practices documents available from several sources (e.g., NIOSH 2009).

CONCLUSIONS

Significant exposures to nanoscale particles and fibers may be generated in several scenarios during manufacturing and post-processing of advanced composites, especially during handling of raw powders, agitation, cutting, drilling, mixing, blending, etc. Monitoring of such exposures, especially for novel processes and technologies without baseline exposure data, is a necessary first step in the recognition and subsequent control of such exposures. The exposure data presented here should serve as a reminder to the materials scientists and engineers of the need to monitor exposures and to adopt a proactive attitude towards promoting and creating a safer work environment for students and researchers.

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